

KNOWLEDGE ON PEACE EDUCATION AND CONFLICT RESOLUTION SKILLS AMONG EDUKASYON SA PAGPAPAKATAO (ESP) TEACHERS

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Knowledge on Peace Education and Conflict Resolution Skills among *Edukasyon Sa Pagpapakatao (ESP) Teachers*

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Abstract

Peace education promotes the knowledge, skills and attitudes to help people prevent conflict occurring, resolve conflicts peacefully, or create conditions for peace. Thus, this study was conducted to determine the influence of knowledge on Peace Education to conflict resolution skills of the the *Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao* teachers of Cluster 3 schools, Department of Education, Division of Davao City. The descriptive-correlational research design under the quantitative research was used in the study. This design sought to find out the relationship between the teachers' knowledge on Peace Education and the teacher's conflict resolution skills. The first instrument used was a researcher made rating scale to determine the level of knowledge of the teachers on Peace Education. The second questionnaire was also self-assessment which was used to measure the conflict resolution skills of the teachers. The results showed that the knowledge on Peace Education was described as above average. On the other hand, the conflict resolution skills of the teachers were interpreted to be a high level. Moreover, data showed that there is a significant relationship between knowledge on Peace Education and conflict resolution skills of *Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao* teachers. Furthermore, results revealed that the indicators Cultivating Inner Peace, Promoting Human Rights and Responsibilities and Building Cultural Respect, Reconciliation and Solidarity significantly predict the conflict resolution skill of the teachers. Recommendations are geared towards the integration of peace education to all subject areas.

Keywords: *peace education, conflict resolution skills*

Introduction

Peace education has gained increasing attention in recent years, reflecting a growing recognition of the importance of fostering a culture of peace and nonviolence in educational settings. Scholarly discourse on peace education has expanded, delving into various dimensions of its theory, practice, and impact. Education is the only means which can generate interest, values, aesthetics, and other qualities which are necessary to bring peace in human mind. Hence, teachers play a vital role in providing awareness and development of peace education among the citizen of the nation.

UNESCO (2012) defines peace education as the process that fosters knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values, aiming to bring about behavioral changes enabling individuals to prevent both overt and structural conflict, resolve disputes peacefully, and create conditions conducive to peace at various levels—ranging from intrapersonal to international. Furthermore, Askerov (2010) stresses peace education's primary goal of instilling a commitment to peaceful approaches within human consciousness. As Askerov argues, the overarching objective of peace education surpasses the cessation of violence; rather, it seeks to psychologically prepare individuals to recognize how nonviolence can form the basis for a just and sustainable future.

In recent years, there has been a surge in global terrorism, including a rise in such incidents within Malaysia (Khairudin, 2019). Despite numerous conflicts and wars causing immense casualties across diverse backgrounds, achieving true peace seems more like rhetoric than a realistic goal in the modern world. While peace is commonly perceived as the absence of war, UNESCO (2014) emphasizes that building defenses for peace begins in the minds of individuals and requires multifaceted efforts integrated into various aspects of human life.

Presently, in the Philippines various forms of violence and conflict prevail, encompassing state violence against civilians, clan-related conflicts, political and armed disputes involving nationalist/separatist groups in Mindanao and the Sulu Archipelago, a communist-inspired guerrilla campaign in western Mindanao, violent extremist and criminal activities, anti-drug vigilantism, other criminal violence, domestic and gender-based violence, protests, election-related violence, and local conflicts over resources and community rights (Herbert, 2019). Moreover, Sapao and Dacles (2021) discussed in their findings in the study of a group at the Philippine Women's University School of Social Work showed that at least five out of 10 children in Grades 1-3, seven out of 10 in Grades 4-6 and 6 out of 10 in high school have experienced violence in school. Verbal abuse, including ridicule, teasing, being shouted at or cursed is the most prevalent form of violence at all levels with male children more likely to experience physical violence. The victims' peers, more than adults, are the perpetrators and most incidents go unreported due to fear of retribution.

Moreover, children in Mindanao are not exempted from the challenges of conflict, abuse, war, and poverty. According to Arenas (2019), the Mindanao State University - Maguindanao Integrated Laboratory Science High School is recognized as a Peace School in Mindanao under the Act for Peace Program. Located in a region marked by poverty, limited privileges for children, and frequent conflicts in nearby municipalities, the school faces challenges stemming from lawless elements, tribal clashes, and misunderstandings. These factors collectively contribute to the lower academic performance of students in the province and region. Schools of Peace,

therefore, should strengthen the academic, ethical, and peace foundations of each learner by integrating peace into various disciplines within the curriculum.

Addressing the surge in global terrorism and diverse forms of violence and conflict in Malaysia and the Philippines requires a comprehensive approach. Initiatives should focus on fostering a culture of peace through multifaceted efforts that encompass education, community engagement, and mental well-being. Integrating peace education into school curricula, as demonstrated by initiatives like the Mindanao State University - Maguindanao Integrated Laboratory Science High School's recognition as a Peace School, becomes crucial in bridging the gap and equipping students with conflict resolution skills, thereby contributing to a more peaceful and just future. This holistic strategy aims to counter violence, promote understanding, and build a resilient society that can navigate and transform conflicts peacefully.

In conclusion, there is a need to create teachers as peace makers and peace builders through peace education. As the researcher, a critical part of this mission is to create something that is of use in the field and serve as a resource for teachers and curriculum designers to optimize students learning through peace education. Conflict resolution skills are integral to peace education, equipping individuals to navigate conflicts peacefully and contribute to a culture of understanding. The integration of conflict resolution skills into peace education not only empowers individuals to manage interpersonal conflicts but also aligns with the broader goal of cultivating a just and sustainable future through peaceful means. This would also invite educators to think seriously about how to support teachers to incorporate and intensify peace education into their professional development sessions. Furthermore, this study seeks to shed light on the benefits that educators may acquire in investigating the influence of peace education to the conflict resolution skills of the Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers. This study will help them to be better equipped in assisting students in increasing their abilities and attain peace in school.

Research Questions

This study is proposed to investigate the influence of knowledge on Peace Education to the conflict resolution skills among Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (ESP) teachers. Furthermore, this aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of teachers' knowledge on Peace Education in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. cultivating inner peace;
 - 1.2. living in harmony with the earth;
 - 1.3. promoting human rights and responsibilities;
 - 1.4. building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity;
 - 1.5. living with justice and compassion; and
 - 1.6. dismantling the culture of war?
2. What is the level of teachers' Conflict Resolution skills in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. accommodating;
 - 2.2. avoiding;
 - 2.3. compromising;
 - 2.4. collaborating; and
 - 2.5. competing?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the knowledge on Peace and Conflict Resolution Skills among Eedukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (ESP) teachers?
4. What indicator of peace education significantly influences conflict resolution skills among Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (ESP) teachers, particularly cluster 3, Division of Davao City?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design under the quantitative research. According to Creswell (2009), quantitative research is done through data collection which can be quantified and subjected to a statistical treatment to support or refute a hypothesis. This type of research also entails data gathering processes that is usually numerical; thus, researchers would then employ mathematical models and statistical tools in their methodology of data analysis. Inquiry methods are usually used by the researchers to fully align their methodology with the statistical data collection.

Researchers evaluate two variables in a correlational study model and evaluate whether there is a statistical connection between the two without regulating external or external variables. Furthermore, Seeram (2019) stated that correlational research is commonly employed when the reason of the study is to find out which variables are connected or related. Thus, it is like investigating for variables which that interact with each other.

The goal of the researcher is to analyze how one affects the other or how they do not. The correlational design is appropriate for the current study because it seeks to find out the relationship between two variables, the teachers' knowledge on peace education and conflict resolution skills.

Respondents

In choosing the respondents, the researcher used the simple random sampling or also called as representative sampling. It is meant to be an unbiased representation of a group and is considered a fair way to select a sample from a larger population (Csikszentmihalyi & Larson, 2014). Furthermore, this manner of selection serves convenience to the researcher. The respondents of this study were the Eduskasyon sa Pagpapakatao (ESP) teachers of Cluster 3 schools of Division of Davao City. The respondents were randomly selected to match the need of the study. The target total number of teacher-respondents was 100.

Moreover, this study was conducted at ten (10) different public schools in Davao City particularly in Cluster 3 schools. These schools are Maa National High School (Maa NHS), GSIS Heights National High School (GSIS NHS), Matina Pangi National High School (MPNHS), Dumoy National High School (DNHS), Catalunan Pequeno National High School (CPNHS), Langub National High School (LNHS), Magtuod National High School (MNHS), Mabini National High School (Mabini NHS), Davao City Special National High School (DCSNHS) and Jesus J. Soriano National High School (JJNHS). The study was conducted to the said schools to achieve the target number of respondents of the study.

Instrument

The researcher used two self-assessment questionnaires. The first research instrument was a researcher made rating scale on the knowledge on peace education. This was to ensure its alignment to the specific content. The instrument was self-rating scale to determine their level of knowledge on peace education. It was used to determine the level of knowledge of ESP teachers on peace education. The questionnaire was based on the six petals of peace education namely: cultivating inner peace; living in harmony with the earth; promoting human rights and responsibilities; building cultural respect; reconciliation and solidarity; living with justice and compassion; and dismantling the culture of war. Each indicator in the first questionnaire contains five (5) statements to which the respondents must choose from 1-5, 5 being the highest. The statements of this questionnaire were checked and validated by experts to know the statements to be included in the final questionnaire. With a reliability test result of 0.88 indicates a high level of consistency and dependability in the measurements, suggesting strong internal reliability and consistent results upon repeated use of the tool.

The survey was a 5-item Likert scale, and it includes the expressions, SD: “Strongly disagree”, D: “Disagree.”, N: “Neither agree nor disagree.”, A: “Agree”, and SA: “Strongly Agree.” While the answer “Strongly Disagree” is represented with the number (1), the answer “Strongly Agree” is represented with the number five (5).

The second survey instrument was used to measure the conflict resolution skills of the teachers. The instrument was adapted from the “Conflict Resolution Skills” scale that was developed by Rahim to determine conflict resolution skills and adapted by Vatansever and Yilmaz in 2016. Investigation of primary school teachers’ conflict resolution skills in terms of different variables. The questionnaire includes five (5) domains namely: accommodating, avoiding, compromising, collaborating, and competing. This questionnaire was validated by experts, pilot tested and reliability tested. Then, revisions were made based on the results. Each indicator contains ten (10) statements to be rated by the respondents. The statements of this questionnaire were checked and validated by experts to know the statements to be included in the final questionnaire. With a reliability test result of 0.91, the interpretation indicates a very high level of consistency and dependability, suggesting that the data or assessment tool used demonstrates internal reliability and is likely to yield consistent results upon repeated use.

The survey was a 5-item Likert scale, and it includes the expressions, SD: “Strongly disagree”, D: “Disagree.”, N: “Neither agree nor disagree.”, A: “Agree”, and SA: “Strongly Agree.” While the answer “Strongly Disagree” is represented with the number (1), the answer “Strongly Agree” is represented with the number five (5).

Before the administration of the evaluation instruments, external validators reviewed the relevance and validity of each item. Then, modifications to the instrument were done by the researcher based on the experts’ reviews and suggestions. Following this step, the validated instrument was tried-out to test the reliability of the said instrument.

Procedure

The following procedures were observed and done to conduct the study:

First, to commence this research endeavor, the researcher asked first permission from the dean of the Graduate School, Dr. Pablo S. Busquit, to conduct of the study. Second, the researcher sought approval by writing a letter address to Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) of Davao City, Dr. Maria Ines C. Asuncion, and to the PSDS of Cluster 3 school, Dr. Fortunato B. Sagayno. After the approval, another letter was sent to the principals of the different schools asking for permission to conduct the study in their respective schools. Third, the two research instruments were validated by one internal and two external experts. After validation, pilot testing and reliability test were done. Fourth, once granted permission, the researcher scheduled the date and time of the survey to the selected teachers of the said school.

The researcher was present during the administration of the survey to explain technical terms and to answer the respondents’ inquiries. Lastly, the answered survey questionnaires were collected and reviewed for analysis. The gathered data were tallied, analyzed and subjected to statistical analysis by the designated statistician using statistical treatments.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used for this study.

Mean. In this study, mean was to identify the common answers of the students. Mean is defined as the sum of all scores divided by the number of cases (Aclao, Cabrera & Colegado, 2013). Mean is considered as the best measure for regular distribution because it is the most reliable, most stable and with the least probable error.

Pearson r Test. The Pearson Product- Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyze if a relationship exists between the study's variables. Specifically, this was used to investigate if relationship between knowledge on peace education to the conflict resolution skills of the Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers. In addition, if proven, this may also explain how much the independent variable influences the dependent variable.

Multiple Regression Analysis. The multiple regression analysis was employed by the researchers to predict the specific indicators of knowledge on peace education that mostly affects teachers' conflict resolution skills. It also determined the extent of influence of knowledge on peace education to the conflict resolution skills of the Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers and to know whether the correlation is positive or negative as indicated by the value of the result (Broto, 2007).

Ethical Considerations

Research ethics is significant for academic integrity, human rights and dignity, and collaboration between science and society. These principles make sure that participations in studies are voluntary, informed, and safe for research subjects and respondents (Bhandari, 2021).

The researcher ensured that the principles of research ethics are followed. These includes voluntary participation, informed consent, anonymity, confidentiality, potential for harm, and results communication. To ensure ethical consideration, the researcher gave an informed consent form to the respondents of the study. The form includes purpose of the research, type of research intervention, participation selection, voluntary participation, procedures, duration, risks, benefits, confidentiality, sharing the results, right to refuse or withdraw and the researcher's contact information.

Purpose of the Research. The researcher ensured that participants were informed of the purpose of this study. The objective of this study is to know if there is a relationship between the knowledge on peace education and the conflict resolution skills of Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (ESP) Teachers of cluster 3, Division of Davao City.

Type of Research Intervention. The researcher sees to it that the respondents will be informed on the type of research intervention used in the study. This research is quantitative in nature and will use a survey questionnaire to collect data from the teachers' response. The researcher personally asked the identified respondents to collect the necessary data. Then the collected data was statistically treated and was interpreted by the researcher.

Participation Selection. The researcher ensured that the respondents were informed that they are chosen to participate in this study because they qualify to the criterion set for this study. The participants who agreed to participate in the study were asked some questions through a survey questionnaire.

Voluntary Participation. This study values the free choice of an individual. Thus, the researcher informed the respondents that if they want to withdraw or decline from participating in this research, he/she can do so anytime. They were informed that that choosing not to participate in this research would not affect their performance rating in school and that their decision for the participation is voluntary.

Procedures. The researcher ensured that the respondents were informed of the procedures of this quantitative research. They were informed that they will answer survey questionnaires in gathering information. They were also informed that name is not required to be filled in and other sensitive information will be kept confidential. Moreover, if respondents does not want to answer an item in the survey questionnaire, he/she can skip the item and proceed to next item.

Duration. Teachers participation in this research was the duration of his/her response to the survey questionnaire. Follow- up were done afterwards.

Risks. The pandemic causes health risk to all the people in the world. The researcher assured that risk in this study was lessen because the researcher and the respondents did not meet personally. All communication between the researcher and respondents were done through their school heads. If there were questions that were too personal or sensitive, respondents were not forced to answer the questions. He/she could also cease to participate if the survey questionnaire made him/her uncomfortable.

Benefits. The researcher made sure that the respondents was informed of the benefits of the study.

Confidentiality. The researcher ensured that the research maintains confidentiality of data with respect to both information about the teacher-respondents and the information he/she shares. The name of the schools was not mentioned. The researcher controlled all responses of the questionnaire and was strict in keeping it confidential and can only be accessible to the researcher.

Sharing the Results. The researcher ensured that nothing that the teacher-respondents answers were shared to anyone except for the

researcher. The researcher made sure that nothing was attributed to the respondents directly by name. The additional knowledge that the researcher got from this study were shared to the respondents before it was made available to the public. Each participant was to check and have a copy of summary of the results.

Right to Refuse or Withdraw. The respondents were informed of their involvement in this research is fully voluntary. He/she did not have to take part in this research if he/she does not wish to do so. He/she may change his/her mind later and stop participating even if he/she agreed earlier. The researcher assured that if the respondents choose to participate, none of this affected his/her performance.

Contact information. The researcher provided contact number and email address in case the respondents had questions, clarifications, or concerns about this research. The respondents were also given the researcher's messenger account for easier access.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analyses and interpretations of the data gathered by the researcher. Discussions are presented categorically based on the sequence of the statement of the problem in the first chapter.

Knowledge on Peace Education of E.S.P. Teachers

The first objective of this study was to measure and determine the level of knowledge on peace education of Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers of Cluster 3 schools of the Department of Education, Division of Davao City. In line with this aim, Tables 1-7 provides the answer to this objective.

Table 1. *Level of Knowledge of E.S.P. Teachers in terms of Cultivating Inner*

No.	Cultivating Inner Peace...	Mean	Descriptive Level
1	allows people to evaluate their own physical, emotional, and spiritual states as well as the interplay between micro and macro conflicts.	3.70	High
2	means strengthening one's inner resources of faith, love and hope, and one's personal vision and capacities.	4.36	High
3	is characterized by self-respect and a recognition of one's own dignity as a human being.	4.27	High
4	enables a person to face life challenges with an inner equilibrium because he/she is convinced of his/her intrinsic worth and purpose.	4.23	High
5	improves our relationships with others.	4.66	Very High
	Overall	4.25	High

Shown in the Table 1 is the knowledge of E.S.P. teachers on cultivating inner peace with an overall description level of high according to its mean (4.25). Among the six indicators, this is the third highest indicator. This asserts that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on this petal of peace education. In the first statement, "cultivating inner peace allows people to evaluate their own physical, emotional, and spiritual states as well as the interplay between micro and macro conflicts", got a lowest mean rating (3.70) with a high description level. The second statement, "cultivating inner peace means strengthening one's inner resources of faith, love and hope, and one's personal vision and capacities", also yielded high description because of a high mean rating (4.36). The third statement, "cultivating inner peace is characterized by self-respect and a recognition of one's own dignity as a human being", revealed a high description level because of the mean rating (4.27).

While the fourth statement, "cultivating inner peace enables a person to face life challenges with an inner equilibrium because he/she is convinced of his/her intrinsic worth and purpose", resulted to a high description level with an extreme mean rating (4.23). Finally, the last statement, "Cultivating inner peace improves our relationships with others", got the highest mean rating (4.66) with a description level of very high. This means teachers always show excellent and exemplary knowledge on this specific statement. Considering the data above, it implies that teachers acknowledge the importance of having inner peace in resolving conflicts.

This finding is in line with the pronouncement of Kester (2010) that education for inner peace allows people to evaluate their own physical, emotional, and spiritual states as well as the interplay between micro and macro conflicts. Saada (2020) also said that discussions on peace advocacy involve the concept of inner or personal peace, emphasizing that peace originates within everyone. Personal peace revolves around self-development and mastery, drawing on spirituality as a source of strength, whether it is rooted in religious beliefs or secular principles. Saada underscores that, regardless of religious or philosophical differences, the commonality of our shared humanity forms a foundational aspect of personal peace. This was also supported by Mische (2001), wherein the transformation that people aimed for should extend beyond societal changes; it should also serve as inspiration for external actions. She asserts that inner and outer transformations are interconnected facets of a unified whole.

Hence, fostering inner peace involves fortifying internal reserves such as faith, love, hope, and personal vision for constructing external peace. Inner and external peace mutually nourish each other, emphasizing the incongruence of claiming inner peace without addressing violent realities in the environment. Recognizing the impact of a disorderly external environment underscores the importance of simultaneously working towards both inner and outer peace, urging the concurrent nurturing of personal tranquility and contributions to societal harmony. In cultivating inner peace, individuals can cultivate resilience through mindfulness practices and self-reflection, allowing them to navigate challenges with a composed spirit. Consequently, as individuals strive for both personal serenity and a

harmonious society, the integration of inner strength and social responsibility becomes imperative, creating a powerful synergy that fosters peace.

Table 2. *Level of Knowledge of E.S.P. Teachers in terms of Living in Harmony with the Earth*

No.	<i>Living in Harmony with the Earth</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
1.	includes fostering global stewardship.	4.48	High
2.	promotes simple living.	4.32	High
3.	supports in combating the environmental degradation that accompanies unsustainable development and war.	3.91	High
4.	fosters the well-being of the planet, humans, animals, and plant life simultaneously.	4.61	Very High
5.	recognizes the rights of nature in the context of the promotion of sustainable development.	4.39	High
Overall		4.34	High

Shown in Table 2 is the knowledge of E.S.P. teachers on living in harmony with the earth. Among the six indicators in the knowledge on peace education, results showed that living in harmony with the earth got the highest mean rating (4.34) which has a description level of high. This means that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on this petal of peace education. In the first statement, “living in harmony with the earth includes fostering global stewardship”, got a high mean rating (4.48) which has a high description level. The second statement, “living in harmony with the earth promotes simple living”, got a great mean rating (4.32) which also has a high description level. The third statement, “living in harmony with the earth supports in combating the environmental degradation that accompanies unsustainable development and war”, resulted into an eminent mean rating (3.91) with a high description level. The last statement, “living in harmony with the Earth recognizes the rights of nature in the context of the promotion of sustainable development”, yielded a substantial mean rating (4.39) with a high description level.

On the other hand, the fourth statement, “living in harmony with the Earth fosters the well-being of the planet, humans, animals, and plant life simultaneously”, got the highest mean rating (4.61) with description level of very high which means that teachers always show excellent and exemplary knowledge on this statement. With respect to the overall mean rating of this section, it implies that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on this indicator. Living in harmony with the Earth includes valuing, loving and caring the environment the most since human beings are part of the Earth. This also means that teachers support the idea of stewardship of the Earth, or environmental stewardship that is the responsible care and use of this planet's resources, recognizing that we are given the privilege of enjoying and caring for things around us.

This finding was supported by Kester (2010) that environmental education includes utilitarian concepts of natural resources and global stewardship, simple living, and the environmental degradation that accompanies development and violent conflict. Further, Tsegay (2016) said globalization, as a significant phenomenon, has impacted all aspects of our lives by intertwining local and global dynamics. It is contended that certain aspects of globalization, notably the rise of a global economy and the advancements in information and communication technologies, have altered the lifestyles and national cultures of citizens. He also argued that while most individuals are aware of the serious consequences of oppressing the planet, only a few engage in reflective analysis to truly understand the gravity of their actions.

On the other hand, Africa (2011) quoted that the World Health Organization (WHO) reveals that outdoor air pollution claims the lives of 3 million individuals annually, with an additional 1.6 million fatalities attributed to indoor pollution. Water pollution is implicated in the deaths of 15 million children under the age of five each year, while vector-borne diseases like malaria result in the daily loss of 1.5 to 2.7 million lives.

Thus, social issues may be intertwined with environmental problems, given that human beings are considered integral components of the planet. Anyone engaging in the oppression of the planet is, in turn, oppressing its entirety, including both the environment and its inhabitants. The disconcerting aspect lies in the fact that humans are predominantly responsible for this oppression, often turning a deaf ear to the planet's messages and disregarding the consequences of their actions. With this, it is important to teach environmental education that incorporates practical concepts related to the responsible use of natural resources, global stewardship, adopting a modest lifestyle, and addressing environmental degradation arising from both development and violent conflict. Moreover, fostering an ecological consciousness is crucial, as it prompts individuals to recognize the intricate web of connections between social, economic, and environmental factors. By instilling a sense of environmental responsibility, societies can collectively work towards sustainable practices, ensuring a balanced coexistence with the planet and fostering a harmonious relationship.

Shown in Table 3 is the knowledge on promoting human rights and responsibilities of E.S.P. teachers. This indicator has gained a great mean rating (3.84) with a high description level. Though this indicator ranked last among the six and it still have a high description level which implies that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on this petal of peace education. This result reveals that teachers show a positive regard towards this indicator.

The first statement, “promoting human rights and responsibilities is directed by the needs, interests, views and wishes of the people”, got a huge mean rating (3.75). Then the second statement, “promoting human rights and responsibilities helps people to have control over their lives and to be fully involved in decisions which affect them”, also obtained a high mean rating (3.70). The third statement, “promoting human rights and responsibilities enables a person to respect and protect the human rights of others”, gained a significant

mean rating (3.61). Then, the fourth statement, “promoting human rights and responsibilities introduces students to their civil, economic, political, cultural and religious rights, among others, and assesses the nature of violations of these rights”, gained a high mean rating (3.50). All these four statements have description level of high which implies that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on these statements. Lastly, the third statement, “promoting human rights and responsibilities teaches a person to treat every people with dignity and respect”, gained a very large mean rating (4.61) with a description level of very high. It means that teachers always show excellent and exemplary knowledge on this particular statement. Looking into the overall mean rating of this section, it implies that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on this indicator of peace education.

Table 3. Level of Knowledge of E.S.P. Teachers in terms of Promoting Human Rights and Responsibilities

No	Promoting Human Rights and Responsibilities	Mean	Descriptive Level
1.	is directed by the needs, interests, views and wishes of the people.	3.75	High
2.	helps people to have control over their lives and to be fully involved in decisions which affect them.	3.70	High
3.	teaches a person to treat every people with dignity and respect.	4.61	Very High
4.	enables a person to respect and protect the human rights of others.	3.61	High
5.	introduces students to their civil, economic, political, cultural and religious rights, among others, and assesses the nature of violations of these rights.	3.50	High
Overall		3.84	High

The result implies the importance of having a very high knowledge on promoting human rights and responsibilities. This notion is supported by Kester (2010) where education for human rights ensures that all students are aware of their civil, economic, political, cultural, and religious rights, among others, and assesses the nature of violations of these inalienable rights (Kester, 2010). An argument by Turan (2020) states that individuals should comprehend the concept of human rights. It is crucial for people to recognize that their rights and freedoms are paramount, and fundamental education on this subject should be imparted through both familial and school-based education. Human rights education equips individuals with the necessary skills to exercise their rights in their daily lives. Within the realm of human rights education, the goal is to furnish students with knowledge about human rights and instill practices for protecting and defending those rights. He also added that human rights education serves as a foundational component of comprehensive social studies education. With this, subjects such as social studies, interdisciplinary religious culture, and ethics education are pivotal in achieving the primary skills and objectives associated with human rights education.

On the other hand, Fuentes et al. (2019) emphasized the significance of a human rights approach in understanding the role of human rights abuses in the causes, dynamics, and consequences of conflict. They argued that if human rights contribute to the problem, they should also be integral to the solution. Applying a human rights perspective to conflict resolution offers a normatively based conceptual framework, providing standards, principles, and values that guide the design and implementation of conflict resolution strategies and processes. They argued that traditionally, human rights and conflict resolution have been studied independently, highlighting their distinct approaches to the immediate goal of peace agreements and the long-term objective of fostering political, economic, and social change. Conflict resolvers may be concerned that key stakeholders could be hesitant to participate in negotiations requiring them to acknowledge moral or criminal responsibility.

With this, education is essential for promoting and safeguarding human rights, encompassing civil and political rights (first generation) and social, economic, and cultural rights (second generation). Proper education acquaints individuals with these fundamental principles and their corresponding rights and obligations. The concept of advancing human rights through education, evolving into third-generation rights, underscores the vital role of education in promoting, protecting, and resolving conflicts related to human rights.

Table 4. Level of Knowledge of E.S.P. Teachers in terms of Building Cultural Respect, Reconciliation and Solidarity

No.	Building Cultural Respect, Reconciliation and Solidarity	Mean	Descriptive Level
1.	values the cultural diversity.	4.45	High
2.	builds an environment free from bias toward a particular race, gender, or physical appearance.	4.32	High
3.	is concerned with interactions between differing groups and cultural norms, and national and international institutions that perpetuate violence or foster peace.	4.02	High
4.	contributes to the co-existence and unity between different cultural groups around the world.	3.98	High
5.	shows the relevance of intercultural respect, reconciliation, and solidarity.	4.68	Very High
Overall		4.29	High

Shown in the Table 4 is the knowledge on building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity of E.S.P. teachers. This is the fourth highest indicator with a huge mean rating (4.29) and a description level of high which reveals that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on this petal of peace education. The first statement, “building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity values the cultural diversity”, gained a mean high rating (4.45). While the second statement, “building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity builds an environment free from bias toward a particular race, gender, or physical appearance”, also gained a large mean rating (4.32). Then the third statement, “building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity is concerned with interactions between differing groups and cultural norms, and national and international institutions that perpetuate violence or foster peace”, gained a considerable mean rating (4.02). The fourth statement, “building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity contributes to the co-

existence and unity between different cultural groups around the world”, also gained a considerable mean rating (3.98). These four statements have a description level of high which means that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on these four accounts. Lastly, the statement, “building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity shows the relevance of intercultural respect, reconciliation, and solidarity”, gained a significant mean rating (4.68) which has description level of very high which implies that that teachers always show excellent and exemplary knowledge on this statement. With respect to the overall mean rating of this section, it implies that teacher have exhibit very good and high knowledge on this petal of peace education. This means that teachers have a deep understanding on cultural respect and diversity. This can be referred to as the respect and tolerance that people belonging to one particular culture.

This idea is supported by Kester (2010) that intercultural solidarity is concerned with interactions between differing groups and cultural norms, and national and international institutions that perpetuate oppression. Saada (2020) additionally relates this perspective to multiculturalism, asserting that as individuals increasingly migrate for various reasons such as work, study, or residency, there should be a corresponding mental shift towards recognizing and embracing diversity. Regions with relative peace and abundant opportunities attract a diverse population, altering demographics. With physical closeness and diversity within these places, a cosmopolitan mindset becomes essential to foster unity amid diversity in our interconnected global village. Saada argues that respect and tolerance are fundamental for building and maintaining diversity, serving as safeguards against the pitfalls of homogeneity, ethnocentrism, racism, and xenophobia. Moreover, he emphasizes the need for a multicultural mindset among political leaders to prevent the politicization of majority-minority and diversity issues.

In contrast, Mahan and Mahuna (2017) emphasize the abundance of processes and tools available for conflict resolution, spanning interpersonal, meta-level, and international approaches that enable the constructive resolution of conflicts by learning from diverse cultural perspectives. They argue that conflict resolution is a vital aspect of nurturing robust relationships in our interconnected world. Furthermore, Mahan and Mahuna underscore the significance of empathy and effective communication as central components in conflict resolution, emphasizing the need for individuals to comprehend and appreciate diverse viewpoints. In their view, cultivating conflict resolution skills not only contributes to peaceful coexistence but also promotes a global ethos of cooperation and understanding essential for navigating the complexities of an interconnected world.

Table 5. *Level of Knowledge of E.S.P. Teachers in terms of Living with Justice and Compassion*

No.	Living with Justice and Compassion	Mean	Descriptive Level
1.	deconstructs globalization processes, neoliberalism, and the notion of a commons.	4.11	High
2.	promotes a fundamental part of human love, and a cornerstone of greater social interconnection and humanism.	4.30	High
3.	enables a person to be an active participant of humanity, working for the benefits and good of all people.	4.20	High
4.	teaches deep understanding and empathy of the suffering of another coupled with the wish to relieve it.	4.02	High
5.	explores peace and social justice issues that transcend geographic, national and cultural boundaries, including environmental devastation, systemic violence, war, the refugee crisis, powerlessness and the exclusion of marginalized groups.	3.86	High
Overall		4.10	High

Shown in the Table 5 is the level of knowledge on living with justice and compassion of E.S.P. teachers. This has the second highest mean rating (4.10) with a description level of high. The result revealed that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on this petal of peace education. The first statement, “living with justice and compassion deconstructs globalization processes, neoliberalism, and the notion of a commons”, gained a high mean rating (4.11). While the second statement, “Living with justice and compassion promotes a fundamental part of human love, and a cornerstone of greater social interconnection and humanism”, also obtained a high mean rating (4.30). Then the third statement, “living with justice and compassion enables a person to be an active participant of humanity, working for the benefits and good of all people”, yielded a huge mean rating (4.20). Next is the fourth statement, “living with justice and compassion teaches deep understanding and empathy of the suffering of another coupled with the wish to relieve it”, gained a large mean rating (4.02). Lastly, the fifth statement, “Living with justice and compassion explores peace and social justice issues that transcend geographic, national and cultural boundaries, including environmental devastation, systemic violence, war, the refugee crisis, powerlessness and the exclusion of marginalized groups”, gained a considerable mean rating (3.86). All of these five statements have a description of high which means that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on all of these statements. This conveys that teachers are concerned with educating and giving justice and compassion to people. Compassion is the deep awareness of the suffering of another coupled with the wish to relieve it. Hence, living with justice and compassion also means being aware of different forms oppression.

This notion is concurred with Kester (2010) that this concerns with educating for justice and compassion looks at global markets, capitalism, poverty and gross inequities. Saada (2020) also added that even if we are away from communities riddled by protracted conflict or those coming out of violent conflicts, this only implies we are not in a situation of direct physical violence, but injustice exists in other forms. Indirect forms of violence, such as cultural and structural, exists even in cities and towns where direct armed conflict is absent. Structural violence includes the growing wedge between the rich and the poor, the haves, and have-nots, the educated

and the non-educated, the gated subdivisions versus the slums, and so on. She also added that structural violence exists where the wealth is concentrated in the hands of the few while the majority continues to be illiterate, poor, marginalized and disempowered.

Thus, it is important to have a very high knowledge on justice and compassion since these are pillars that advocate for fairness and empathy within society. These values are constructed through positive thinking, an understanding of human rights, and self-awareness (Amin et al, 2019). In essence, individuals embracing justice and compassion contribute to the establishment of a just and compassionate society by cultivating positive perspectives, upholding human rights, and being conscious of their own actions and impact on others. These principles form the foundation for a harmonious and equitable community.

Table 6. Level of Knowledge of E.S.P. Teachers in terms of Dismantling the Culture of War

No.	Dismantling the Culture of War	Mean	Descriptive Level
1.	concerned with mitigating all support for the war system.	3.68	High
2.	prevents competitive games and gender oppression.	4.45	High
3.	is against defense spending and oppressive security systems.	3.93	High
4.	prohibits the sale of toys that mimic violence and teach children destructive behaviors.	3.82	High
5.	includes dissolving weapons access as well as disarming the mind from hate.	3.30	Average
Overall		3.84	High

Shown in the Table 6 is the level of knowledge on dismantling the culture of war of E.S.P. teachers. The last indicator gained the same mean rating (3.84). Though this indicator ranked last among the six and it still have a high description level which implies that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on these two petals of peace education. The first statement, “dismantling the culture of war is concerned with mitigating all support for the war system”, obtained a considerable mean rating (3.68). The second statement, “dismantling the culture of war prevents competitive games and gender oppression”, got a significant mean rating (4.45). While the third statement, “dismantling the culture of war is against defense spending and oppressive security systems”, resulted into a considerable mean rating (3.93). Then the fourth statement, “dismantling the culture of war prohibits the sale of toys that mimic violence and teach children destructive behaviors”, gained a high mean rating (3.82). These four statements have a description level of high which implies that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on these statements. Lastly, the statement, “dismantling the culture of war includes dissolving weapons access as well as disarming the mind from hate”, obtained a significant mean rating (3.30) which has a description level of average. This implies that teachers always show average and balanced knowledge on this particular statement. However, looking into the overall mean rating of this section, it shows that teachers which implies that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on this petal of peace education. This result revealed that teachers agreed that this is concerned with reducing, limiting, or abolishing weapon which supports war.

This notion is supported by Kester (2010) where dismantling a culture of war is concerned with mitigating all support for the war system, including competitive games, gender oppression, defense spending, and security systems. According to Saada (2020), war and violence have always found justification. But we should not allow this to continue. As such, she said that we need to advocate for the widening of democratic spaces where grievances can be resolved through active non-violence or through non-killing. Therefore, the challenge for state and society is how to pursue its goal and address its challenges without resorting to killing or violence. Conflict is natural, killing is not. She also added that justice and compassion can be pursued without engaging in violence or war. There is a need to be critical about the martial solution to people’s grievances.

Table 7. Summary on the Level of Knowledge on Peace Education of E.S.P. Teachers

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
1.	Cultivating Inner Peace	4.25	High
2.	Living in Harmony with the Earth	4.34	High
3.	Promoting Human Rights and Responsibilities	3.84	High
4.	Building Cultural Respect, Reconciliation and Solidarity	4.29	High
5.	Living with Justice and Compassion	4.10	High
6.	Dismantling the Culture of War	3.84	High
Overall		4.11	High

Shown in the Table 7 is the overall knowledge on peace education level of Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers is found to have a large mean rating (4.11) with a description level of high. Among the six indicators, living in harmony with the earth got the highest mean (4.34). The said it was followed by building cultural respect, reconciliation, and solidarity with also a huge mean rating (4.29). The third highest indicator is cultivating inner peace with a high mean rating (4.25). Living with justice and compassion ranked fourth among the indicators and it has a high mean (4.10). The last two indicators namely promoting human rights and responsibilities and dismantling the culture of war have gained the same mean rating (3.84). All the six indicators have a descriptive level of high.

The result above means that teachers exhibit very good and high knowledge on the six petals of peace education. E.S.P. teachers are deemed to have a more knowledge on the different petals of peace education. Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers should possess a deep understanding of peace education because it equips them to foster a positive and harmonious learning environment. A high level of knowledge in peace education enables teachers to instill in students the principles of conflict resolution, tolerance, and empathy, essential for building a peaceful society. Such educators serve as role models, imparting not only academic knowledge but also crucial

life skills that contribute to the overall well-being of students. Ultimately, a strong foundation in peace education empowers teachers to shape future generations capable of promoting understanding and cooperation in a diverse and interconnected world, as well as making collaborative efforts of conflict resolution. Hence, a very high result on the knowledge of peace education was evident by the results above. This proficiency in shows a fosters positive and inclusive environment but also equips students.

Level of Conflict Resolution Skills of E.S.P. Teachers

The second objective of this study was to measure and determine the level of conflict resolution skills of Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers of Cluster 3 schools of the Department of Education, Division of Davao City. Tables 8-13 provide the answer to this objective.

Table 8. Level of Conflict Resolution Skills of E.S.P. Teachers in terms of Accommodating

No.	Accommodating	Mean	Descriptive Level
1.	I am aware of the other person may need to feel in control of the conflict.	4.16	High
2.	I feel that it is okay to agree to disagree on specific issues in a conflict.	4.27	High
3.	I try to make people feel comfortable when meeting with them about a conflict.	4.30	High
4.	In order not to harm the relationship, I may temporarily put aside some of my feelings.	4.18	High
5.	In conflict my reactions are based on how I think the other party perceives me.	3.98	High
6.	I may not get what I want, but it is a small price to pay for keeping the peace	4.41	High
7.	I try to be aware of how my negative and positive self-perceptions influence the way I talk.	4.34	High
8.	I state my true feelings when dealing with conflict.	4.43	High
9.	I overlook my partners anger in order to focus on the real issues to conflict.	4.09	High
10.	I try to meet the expectations of others.	3.77	High
Overall		4.19	High

Shown in the Table 8 is the level of accommodating skills of E.S.P. teachers. This is the third highest indicator for conflict resolution skills with a high mean rating (4.18) and a high description level, this implies that teachers always show very good conflict resolution skills especially on this strategy resolving the conflict. This further means that teachers perceive themselves as very good in cooperating with the other party in solving conflicts. The first statement, “I am aware of the other person may need to feel in control of the conflict”, obtained a high mean rating (4.16). The second statement, “I feel that it is okay to agree to disagree on specific issues in a conflict”, also gained a huge mean rating (4.27). The third statement, “I try to make people feel comfortable when meeting with them about a conflict”, also gained a large mean rating (4.30). The fourth statement, “In order not to harm the relationship, I may temporarily put aside some of my feelings”, gained a huge mean rating (4.18).

Moreover, the fifth statement, “In conflict my reactions are based on how I think the other party perceives me”, gained a great mean rating (3.98). The sixth statement, “I may not get what I want, but it is a small price to pay for keeping the peace”, gained a significant mean rating (4.41). The seventh statement, “I try to be aware of how my negative and positive self-perceptions influence the way I talk”, resulted into a large mean rating (4.34). The eighth statement, “I state my true feelings when dealing with conflict”, gained a high mean rating (4.43). The ninth statement, “I overlook my partners anger in order to focus on the real issues to conflict”, yielded a large mean rating (4.09). The tenth and the last statement, “I try to meet the expectations of others”, gained a considerable mean rating (3.77). All the statements in this section have a description level of high which means that that teachers always show very good conflict resolution skills especially on this strategy of resolving the conflict. This idea is concurred by Chandolia and Anastasiou (2020) that the accommodating style accommodates concerns of ‘others first’ instead of giving one’s own interests top priority. The smoothing technique is appropriate when it is crucial to provide a relief that is temporal from conflict and/or when the problem is not meaningful to one person compared to others.

As explained by Mosadeghrad and Mojibafan (2019), the accommodating style is characterized by being unassertive yet cooperative, representing a lose-win strategy. In this approach, one party willingly sets aside their own interests to address and satisfy the concerns of the other party.

Table 9. Level of Conflict Resolution Skills of E.S.P. Teachers in terms of Avoiding

No.	Avoiding	Mean	Descriptive Level
1.	I am afraid to enter into confrontations.	3.59	High
2.	I feel that in conflicts someone will get hurt.	3.55	High
3.	I feel that conflict is a negative experience.	3.48	Average
4.	I avoid hard feelings by keeping my disagreements with others to myself.	3.86	High
5.	When I find myself in an argument, I usually say very little and try to leave as soon as possible.	3.30	Average
6.	Being at odds with other people makes me feel uncomfortable and anxious.	3.34	Average
7.	There are times when I let others take responsibility for solving the problem.	2.16	Low
8.	I try to avoid creating unpleasantness for myself.	2.77	Average
9.	I avoid taking positions which would create controversy.	3.61	High
10.	I sulk and walk away from others.	2.98	Average
Overall		3.26	Average

Shown in the Table 9 is the level of avoiding skills of E.S.P. teachers. The second indicator which ranked low for conflict resolution skills is avoiding. With an normal mean rating (3.26) with an average description level, this implies that teachers show balanced conflict resolution skills especially on this strategy of resolving the conflict. The first statement, “I am afraid to enter into confrontations”, yielded a considerable mean rating (3.59) with a description level of high. The second statement, “I feel that in conflicts someone will get hurt”, obtained a high mean rating (3.55) with a description level of high. The third statement, “I feel that conflict is a negative experience”, gained a considerable mean rating (3.48) with a description level of average. The fourth statement, “I avoid hard feelings by keeping my disagreements with others to myself”, also gained a considerable mean rating (3.86) with a description level of high.

Moreover, the fifth statement, “When I find myself in an argument, I usually say very little and try to leave as soon as possible”, gained an average mean rating (3.30) with a description level of average. The sixth statement, “Being at odds with other people makes me feel uncomfortable and anxious”, gained a normal mean rating (3.34) with a description level of average. The seventh statement, “There are times when I let others take responsibility for solving the problem”, gained a relatively low mean rating (2.16) with a description level of low. The eighth statement, “I try to avoid creating unpleasantness for myself”, gained an average mean rating (2.77) with a description level of average. The ninth statement, “I avoid taking positions which would create controversy”, gained a considerable mean rating (3.61) with a description level of high. The tenth and last statement, “I sulk and walk away from others”, gained a low mean rating (2.98) with a description level of average. However, with respect to the overall mean of this indicator which has description level of average, it implies that teachers show balanced conflict resolution skills especially on this strategy of resolving the conflict. This further means that teachers acknowledge themselves to use avoidance not so often in solving conflicts. Avoiding is the least frequently used strategy in dealing with conflicts.

This idea is supported by Chandolia and Anastasiou (2020) who said that where avoiding is a managing conflict style whereby an individual fails to adequately address a conflict but instead postpones, withdraws, or sidesteps. In most cases, individuals will tend to avoid conflict due to fear of getting involved in the dispute or they may lack the confidence in their managing conflict skills. Nevertheless, Iligan (2020) suggests that utilizing this style can be beneficial for achieving a temporary calming effect following an intense conflict. Taking a brief pause to allow emotions to settle and adopting an accommodating approach may contribute to a more constructive resolution.

With this, avoidance skills in conflict resolution are crucial for several reasons. Firstly, they provide individuals with an opportunity to de-escalate emotionally charged situations by stepping back and allowing tensions to subside. This prevents impulsive reactions that can further intensify the conflict. Secondly, avoiding immediate confrontation allows parties involved to gain perspective, reflect on the underlying issues, and consider alternative solutions without the pressure of the moment. Thirdly, it can be a strategic choice when the timing or context is not conducive to a productive discussion, enabling a more thoughtful and constructive approach later. Furthermore, avoidance can serve as a temporary measure to prevent exacerbation of conflicts that may not be ready for resolution, giving individuals time to prepare for a more effective dialogue. Lastly, when used judiciously, avoidance skills can contribute to a more sustainable and positive conflict resolution process, fostering long-term understanding and cooperation.

Table 10. *Level of Conflict Resolution Skills of E.S.P. Teachers in terms of Compromising*

No.	Compromising	Mean	Descriptive Level
1.	In order not to harm the relationship, I may temporarily put aside some of my own less important personal wants.	4.43	High
2.	I bargain to resolve conflict.	4.70	Very High
3.	At the end of a conflict, it matters to me that the other person's needs have been met.	4.80	Very High
4.	I feel for a relationship to last, the needs of both parties must be considered.	4.41	High
5.	When I prepare to meet to discuss a conflict, I try to arrange for a mutually acceptable solution.	4.20	High
6.	In a conflict I strive to distinguish between real needs and desires.	4.55	Very High
7.	When in a conflict with someone, I ask them to explain their position.	4.73	Very High
8.	When I resolve a conflict, it improves my relationship.	4.86	Very High
9.	I try to negotiate and adopt a “give-and-take” approach to problem situations.	4.45	High
10.	I share my positive attitude, hoping they will do the same.	4.82	Very High
Overall		4.60	Very High

Shown in the Table 10 is the level of compromising skills of E.S.P. teachers. Among the five indicators of conflict resolution skills, compromising has the highest mean rating (4.60). This entails the description level very high which means that teachers always show exemplary conflict resolution skills especially on this strategy of resolving the conflict. The first statement, “In order not to harm the relationship, I may temporarily put aside some of my own less important personal wants”, gained a large mean rating (4.43) with a description level of high. The second statement, “I bargain to resolve conflict”, also gained a significant mean rating (4.70) with a description level of very high. The third statement, “At the end of a conflict, it matters to me that the other person's needs have been met”, obtained an extreme mean rating (4.80) with a description level of very high. The fourth statement, “I feel for a relationship to last, the needs of both parties must be considered”, gained a large mean rating (4.41) with a description level of high.

Furthermore, the fifth statement, “When I prepare to meet to discuss a conflict, I try to arrange for a mutually acceptable solution”,

gained a huge mean rating (4.20) with a description level of high. The sixth statement, “In a conflict I strive to distinguish between real needs and desires”, also obtained a large mean rating (4.55) with a description level of very high. The seventh statement, “When in a conflict with someone, I ask them to explain their position”, gained a very large mean rating (4.73) with a description level of very high. The eighth statement, “When I resolve a conflict, it improves my relationship”, obtained a significant mean rating of 4.86 with a description level of very high. The ninth statement, “I try to negotiate and adopt a “give-and-take” approach to problem situations”, gained a large mean rating (4.45) with a description level of high. The tenth statement, “I share my positive attitude, hoping they will do the same”, also obtained a very significant mean rating (4.82) with a description level of very high. Moreover, the overall mean rating shows a very high description level which implies that teachers always show exemplary conflict resolution skills especially on this strategy of resolving the conflict. This result implies that teachers are assertive and cooperative in finding an acceptable solution to the matters at hand. The respondents further manifest the necessary personal skills and strategies which are important in dealing and resolving conflicts. Compromising means to make an agreement in an argument in which the people involved reduce their demands or change their opinion in order to agree.

This concept is supported by the pronouncement of Chandolia and Anastasiou (2020) that compromising is a conflict managing approach aimed at finding a solution that is mutually acceptable and expedient and partially satisfies both the involved parties. Further, Mosadeghrad and Mojibafan (2019) cited that individuals using the compromising strategy which are moderate in both assertiveness and cooperativeness aim to find an acceptable solution that satisfies both parties’ concerns partially.

In conclusion, compromising skills are very essential in conflict resolution as they enable teachers to find middle ground and reach mutually acceptable solutions. By embracing compromise, individuals acknowledge the validity of differing perspectives. This collaborative approach fosters cooperation and maintains relationships contributing to effective and sustainable conflict resolution.

Table 11. Level of Conflict Resolution Skills of E.S.P. Teachers in terms of Collaborating

No.	Collaborating	Mean	Descriptive Level
1.	I try to investigate an issue with others to find a solution acceptable to us.	3.80	High
2.	I try to integrate my ideas with those of others to come up with a decision jointly.	4.66	Very High
3.	I try to work with others to find a solution to a problem which satisfy our expectation.	4.89	Very High
4.	I exchange accurate information with others to solve a problem together.	4.39	High
5.	I try to bring all our concerns out in the open so that the issues can be resolved in the best possible way.	4.16	High
6.	I collaborate with others to come up with decisions acceptable to us.	4.20	High
7.	I try to work with others for a proper understanding of a problem.	4.48	High
8.	I strive for a complete and genuine resolution of a conflict rather than settling for a partially implemented solution.	4.75	Very High
9.	I listen with an open mind to alternative options.	4.36	High
10.	In a conflict, I believe there should be no upper-hand.	4.64	Very High
	Overall	4.43	High

Shown in the Table 11 is the level of collaborating skills of E.S.P. teachers. The second highest indicator for conflict resolution skills is collaborating. With the highest mean rating (4.43) and a very high description level, this implies that teachers always show exemplary conflict resolution skills especially on this strategy of resolving the conflict. The first statement, “I try to investigate an issue with others to find a solution acceptable to us”, yielded a considerable mean rating (3.80) with a description level of high. The second statement, “I try to integrate my ideas with those of others to come up with a decision jointly”, gained a large mean rating (4.66) with a description level of very high. The third statement, “I try to work with others to find a solution to a problem which satisfy our expectation”, obtained a very significant mean rating (4.89) with a description level of very high.

Further, the fourth statement, “I exchange accurate information with others to solve a problem together”, gained a large mean rating (4.39) with a description level of high. The fifth statement, “I try to bring all our concerns out in the open so that the issues can be resolved in the best possible way”, yielded a high mean rating (4.16) with a description level of high. The sixth statement, “I collaborate with others to come up with decisions acceptable to us”, gained a huge mean rating (4.20) with a description level of high. The seventh statement, “I try to work with others for a proper understanding of a problem”, also gained a high mean rating (4.48) with a description level of high. The eighth statement, “I strive for a complete and genuine resolution of a conflict rather than settling for a partially implemented solution”, obtained an extreme mean rating (4.75) with a description level of very high. The ninth statement, “I listen with an open mind to alternative options”, gained a large mean rating (4.36) with a description level of high. The tenth statement, “In a conflict, I believe there should be no upper-hand”, gained an extreme mean rating (4.64) with a description level of very high. Moreover, the overall mean has a description level of high which implies that teachers always show exemplary conflict resolution skills especially on this strategy of resolving the conflict. This further means that teachers acknowledge skills and strategies that will help them resolve conflicts. This skill includes integrating approach where identifying the problem is necessary in solving the conflict.

This is supported by Chandolia and Anastasiou (2020) where collaborating approach entails making an effort of working with the other individual in searching for a solution that fully addresses the issue at hand, satisfying all the involved parties. It includes identification of the underlying concerns of one’s opponent and finding the alternatives for meeting the interests of each party. Furthermore,

Mosadeghrad and Mojibafan (2019) said that Collaborating is also assertive and cooperative which is opposite to avoiding. It is a win-win strategy where everyone collaborates and strives to find a solution that fully satisfies both parties' concerns.

In general, collaborating skills are crucial in as they involve a cooperative and integrative approach to finding solutions that satisfy the needs of all parties involved. Through collaboration, individuals harness collective creativity and insights to address the root causes of the conflict, fostering a deeper understanding of each other's perspectives. This process not only results in more sustainable solutions but also builds trust and strengthens relationships. Collaborative conflict resolution is particularly valuable in complex situations where diverse viewpoints and expertise are essential for reaching optimal outcomes.

Table 12. *Level of Conflict Resolution Skills of E.S.P. Teachers in terms of Competing*

No.	Competing	Mean	Descriptive Level
1.	In conflict, I try to dominate the other party.	2.95	Average
2.	I feel the need to control an argument.	3.20	Average
3.	I find it necessary to overpower others to get my own way.	3.36	Average
4.	If I had my way, I win, you lose.	1.61	Very Low
5.	I feel that only my needs are important.	1.41	Very Low
6.	I feel there is just one way to solve a problem.	2.82	Average
7.	When dealing with a conflict I have a pre-determined solution to the outcome.	3.73	High
8.	I feel that winning the war is more important than winning the battle.	3.23	Average
9.	When dealing with a conflict, I have preconceived notions about the other party.	3.84	High
10.	I bring up old issues from the past during a new conflict.	4.02	High
Overall		3.02	Average

Shown in the Table 12 is the last indicator in conflict resolution skills is competing. It is revealed that competing earned a regular mean rating (3.02) which also has an average description level. This means that teachers show balanced conflict resolution skills especially on this strategy of resolving the conflict. Competing is an assertive but not cooperative style in resolving the conflict. The data revealed that respondents used this strategy the least.

This finding is supported by Chandolia and Anastasiou (2020), collaborating-integrating approach entails trying of working with the other individual in searching for a solution that fully addresses the issue at hand, satisfying all the involved parties. It includes identification of the underlying concerns of one's opponent and finding the alternatives for meeting the interests of each party. Furthermore, Mosadeghrad and Mojibafan (2019) also said that Collaborating (assertive and cooperative), opposite to avoiding, is a win-win strategy where everyone collaborates and strives to find a solution that fully satisfies both parties' concerns. It is usually the best style for managing organizational conflicts.

Adopting a competing approach entails pushing one's opinion at the expense of others and maintaining active resistance to the action of the other person. The forcing technique is used in situations whereby one needs to fight for ones' rights/opinion, resisting pressure or aggression (Chandolia & Anastasiou, 2020). Mosadeghrad and Mojibafan (2019) further mentioned that adopting a competing style entails a win-lose strategy, as an individual prioritizes their own concerns potentially at the expense of the other person.

Hence, competing as a conflict resolution skill has both advantages and drawbacks. On the positive side, it can lead to swift decision-making, assertiveness, and clear outcomes, particularly in situations where quick action is necessary. However, the competitive approach may result in winners and losers, fostering resentment and potentially damaging relationships. It often prioritizes individual goals over shared interests, overlooking opportunities for collaboration. Competing may also create a tense and adversarial atmosphere, hindering open communication and problem-solving. Finally, the long-term sustainability of resolutions achieved through competition may be compromised, as they might not address the underlying concerns of all parties involved.

Table 13. *Summary of the Level of Conflict Resolution Skills of E.S.P. Teachers*

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
1.	Accommodating	4.18	High
2.	Avoiding	3.26	Average
3.	Compromising	4.60	Very High
4.	Collaborating	4.43	Very High
5.	Competing	3.02	Average
Overall		3.90	High

Shown in the Table 13 is the overall conflict resolution skills level of Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers was found out to have a considerable mean rating (3.90) with a description level of high. This means that teachers always show very good conflict resolution skills across all domains at all times. On the other hand, the first indicator, accommodating, got a large mean rating (4.18) which has a description level of high. This means that teachers always show very good conflict resolution skills across all domains at all times. While the second indicator, avoiding, gained a normal mean rating (3.26) which has description level of average. This implies that teachers show balanced conflict resolution skills across all domains.

Further, the third indicator, compromising, gained a significant mean rating (4.60) which has description level of very high. This means that teachers always show exemplary conflict resolution skills across all domains. The fourth indicator, collaborating, also obtained a large mean rating (4.43) which has also a description level of very high. This means that teachers always show exemplary conflict resolution skills across all domains. Lastly, the fifth indicator, competing, gained a normal mean rating (3.02) which has description level of average. This implies that teachers show balanced conflict resolution skills across all domains. On this variable, the teachers show very good conflict resolution skills across all domains at all times. This also means that teachers supported the idea that conflict resolution skills are the skills that enable a person to resolve conflict quickly, respectfully, and effectively.

This notion is agreed by Turk (2018) who said that conflict resolution skills is defined as the ability to gain empathy, effective communication, anger management and problem-solving skills. He also said that conflict resolution skills provide opportunity to learn living together and embrace diversity. The level of conflict resolution skills of ESP teachers in this study is divided into five strategies or indicators namely accommodating, avoiding, compromising, collaborating; and competing which are shown in the following sub-tables.

Relationship between Knowledge on Peace Education and Conflict Resolution Skills of E.S.P. Teachers

One important purpose of this study was to determine whether or not the knowledge on peace education significantly relate with the conflict resolution skills of the Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers of the Cluster 3 schools of the Department of Education, Division of Davao City. Furthermore, to answer the question, table 14 presents the following data.

Table 14. *Test of Relationship Between Knowledge on Peace Education and Conflict Resolution Skills of E.S.P. Teachers*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R²</i>	<i>Degree of Relationship</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision at 0.05 level</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Knowledge on Peace Education and Conflict Resolution Skills	0.684	0.468	High	0.00	Significant	Reject H ₀

Shown in the Table 14 is the result which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis; furthermore, this goes to say that there is a significant relationship between knowledge on Peace Education and conflict resolution skills. This implies that the Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers of cluster 3 schools of the Department of Education, Division of Davao City perceive themselves as very good in Peace Education which significantly contributed to their high level of conflict resolution skills. Significantly, the results show how knowledgeable the teachers are on Peace Education. The results also revealed that teachers have also a high level of conflict resolution skills. Hence, the researcher can tell how empowered teachers are to take roles not just inside the school community but also to their own community.

Mishra et al. (2020) asserted the significance of peace education is universally recognized for a safe and prospering future for the world at school level as peace education aims at equipping the future citizens with necessary knowledge, attitude, and skills so that they would acknowledge and respect all kinds of diversity and understand human dignity.

The result above is recognized by the government. Thus, in the hopes of training teachers to become Peace Educators and resolve conflict peacefully, the K12 program has integrated Peace Education in the curriculum. Hence, teachers must be also knowledge on the different Petals of Peace Education.

Indicator of Knowledge on Peace Education that Significantly Predict the Conflict Resolution Skills of E.S.P. Teachers

This section aims to discuss and answer the fourth objective of the study. The Multiple Linear Regression using the Stepwise Method was used to determine which among the indicators of knowledge on peace education significantly predict the conflict resolution skills of E.SP. teachers at a 0.05 level of significance. Furthermore, table 15 presents the significant data to answer the last research question.

The table shows that the indicators cultivating inner peace (B: 0.29; $p < 0.05$); promoting human rights and responsibilities (B: 0.21, $p < 0.05$), and building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity (B: 0.14; $p < 0.05$) of peace education significantly influence the conflict resolution skills of E.S.P. teachers at a 0.05 level of significance. These findings highlight the critical role of incorporating specific aspects of peace education, such as cultivating inner peace, promoting human rights, and building cultural respect, in enhancing the conflict resolution skills of E.S.P. teachers. The statistically significant influence of these indicators underscores the potential impact of targeted educational interventions on fostering a more adept and peace-oriented teaching community.

Shown in the Table 15 is the result which further implies that for every unit increase in the level of cultivating inner peace, promoting human rights and responsibilities, and building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity, the level of conflict resolution skills would increase by as much as 0.29, 0.21, and 0.14 units respectively. In addition, the generated regression model, $WR = 1.53 + 0.29$ (Cultivating inner peace) + 0.29 (Promoting human rights and responsibilities) + 0.14 (Building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity) account as much as 56 percent ($R^2: 0.56$; $p < 0.05$) of the variance or factors that influence the conflict resolution skills of E.S.P. teachers at a 0.05 level of significance.

The first indicator that significantly affects conflict resolution skills of teachers is cultivating inner peace. The data supports that cultivating inner peace is the core of peacebuilding. Inner peace, which means one can have peace within her/himself, allows one to

have a peaceful relationship with others. Hence, allows one to resolve conflict peacefully. Otherwise, the theories of peace from the academicians will be in vain if there is no action for peace.

Table 15. *Indicators of Knowledge on Peace Education that Significantly Affect the Conflict Resolution Skills of E.S.P. Teachers*

Communicative Adaptability	Unstandardized	Standardized	t-stat	p-value	Decision @ 0.05 Level of Significance	
	Coefficient	Coefficient				
	B	SE	Beta			
(Constant)	1.53	0.22		7.05	0.00	Significant
Cultivating Inner Peace	0.29	0.06	0.42	0.52	0.00	Significant
Promoting Human Rights and Responsibilities	0.21	0.05	0.311	0.40	0.00	Significant
Building Cultural Respect, Reconciliation and Solidarity	0.14	0.05	0.22	2.87	0.01	Significant
Regression Model:	WR = 1.53 + 0.29 (Cultivating Inner Peace) + 0.29 (Promoting Human Rights and Responsibilities) + 0.14 (Building Cultural Respect, Reconciliation and Solidarity)					
	R: 0.75 ; R ² : 0.56 ; F: 41.42; p-value: 0.00; Durbin Watson: 2.02					

The idea above is supported by Mische (2001) that the transformation that we should seek not only be the transformation of our society, but also the transformation inspires the outer work. She concludes that the inner and outer transformations are inseparable parts of one whole. There is a growing consensus that there is an intimate connection between our inner state and what we do in our outer spheres. This consistency is the foundation of being a fully integrated person. Thus, cultivating inner peace is essential to conflict resolution.

The second indicator that significantly affects conflict resolution skills of teachers is promoting human rights and responsibilities. The data revealed that promoting and adhering to the human rights and humanitarian law standards can limit the spread of violence, shape how the resolution of the conflict is conducted, and minimize the dehumanization of the enemy. By so doing, they limit the scale of victimhood and grievances. This idea was supported by Fuentes, et. al (2019) who said that the role of human rights abuses in the causes, dynamics, and consequences of conflict illustrate the importance of a human rights approach to conflict resolution. She also added that, if human rights are part of the problem, they must be part of the solution. When applied to conflict resolution, a human rights perspective provides a set of standards, principles, and values that offers guidance in the design and implementation of conflict resolution strategies and processes. Hence, promoting human rights and responsibilities approach is a conceptual framework for conflict resolution processes that is normatively based on international human rights standards.

The third indicator that significantly affects conflict resolution skills of teachers is building cultural respect, reconciliation, and solidarity. The data revealed that building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity is one way of resolving conflicts. This means that respect is the foundation of humane and ethical behavior, and mutual respect underpins good relationships. To have respect for a person involves a fundamental belief in their right to exist, to be heard, and to have the same opportunities as everyone else. It involves recognizing differences, understanding their significance, and responding with interest, politeness and care. This idea was supported Mahan et al. (2017) in which he said that we have countless processes and tools in resolving conflict. It includes interpersonal, meta-level, and international to solve conflict constructively; that is learning from the ways other cultures understand. He added that resolving conflicts is an important part of maintaining healthy relationships in our increasingly interactive world. Saada (2020) also associates this on multiculturalism where we should also be moving mentally towards recognition and upholding of diversity.

The results of this study clearly show the influence of peace education to the conflict resolution skills of the Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers of Cluster 3 schools of the Department of Education, Division of Davao City. This study has been conducted to highlight the influence of peace education on the conflict resolution skills of the Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers. This research was conducted under the assumption that peace education might help teachers play their role as a reformer who understand peace problems and their solutions by having positive attitude. Peace education helps teachers to embrace the needs of students who are culturally diverse and to protect their rights. It is also beneficial to develop positive attitude towards the social justice.

In general, peace education plays a crucial role in fostering and advocating for peace by influencing people's perspectives. Teachers, as influential figures, can address issues and conflicts related to peace by cultivating a peaceful mindset among young individuals through the implementation of peace education. Consequently, the researcher's objective is to organize training sessions for teachers, focusing on peace education and effective conflict resolution strategies.

By empowering teachers with the knowledge and skills to integrate peace education into their classrooms, the researcher aims to create a ripple effect, as these educators, in turn, inspire their students to become advocates for peace in their communities. The goal is to instill a lasting commitment to peaceful coexistence and attain conflict resolution skills by actively practicing effective communication, and negotiation techniques, while seeking to understand diverse perspectives and working collaboratively towards mutually beneficial solutions.

Conclusions

Based from the results of the study, the following conclusions are derived:

The knowledge of Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers is very evident in all petals of peace education. In addition, their knowledge on cultivating inner peace, promoting human rights and responsibilities and building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity is more reflected than the other indicators.

The Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao teachers perceive themselves very good with their conflict resolution skills. This skill is improved when they have cultivated inner peace. Also when they have a very good knowledge in promoting human rights and responsibilities, and building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity.

A high level of significant relationship between knowledge on peace education and conflict resolution skills of students is found out using the statistical treatment of the data. This means that the likelihood of a relationship between two or more variables is caused by something other than chance; there is likelihood that one of the causes of conflict resolution skills of the ESP teachers is their knowledge on peace education.

To improve the conflict resolution skills of the teachers, the knowledge on the six petals of peace education especially cultivating inner peace, promoting human rights and responsibilities, and building cultural respect, reconciliation and solidarity, should be improved.

Based on the conclusions drawn out of the study, the following recommendations are forwarded.

The Department of Education should aid the officials in this department. They should also intensify the implementation of appropriate peace practices and strategies and how it will be achieved. The Department of Education should take a big part in developing and planning of peace education Intervention to ensure that education contributes to the attainment of culture of peace in the country. In addition, they should also provide programs for the teachers that will aid them in teaching and in incorporating peace education and conflict resolution strategies.

The School Administrators should inspire school leaders to consider the integration of peace education to all subject areas. It will help them decide to create activities that will enrich the curriculum to help students achieve culture of peace. It will also help them decide to create a program that can be injected in the intensified professional development given to their educators. Hence, educational institutions especially the Basic Education must take on this vital role by designing an intensified curriculum instruction by integrating peace education in the classroom instruction to attain culture of peace for the betterment of the students.

The teachers should understand the big picture and should align the learning objectives to the school's curriculum. It will help the teachers to design an instruction where the activities can help attain a culture of peace. Furthermore, teachers should learn and live nonviolent approaches to conflict resolution for public and private personnel and community issues.

The students should realize the importance of the culture of peace and conflict resolution skills to their career choices and work readiness in the future. They should always keep in mind that the learning the culture of peace entails learning the different petals of peace education. This will help them prevent the emergence of conflicts and creates conditions for peace in the world.

Moreover, the researcher would like to come up with a program that will include all teachers in Maa National High School. This will be a professional development program for teachers to improve the knowledge on peace education and enhance their skills on conflict resolution.

The future researchers should use the research to enrich the literature about teachers teaching peace education. For the improvement of this study, they can include different indicators. A qualitative or a mixed-research method study is also highly recommended. Finally, this study can be further replicated to involve more schools and increase the validity and reliability of its findings.

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